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COMPARATIVE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Comparative education is a rich analytical tool for educational systems. It helps to sample similarities and differences, broadening the field of analysis and understanding of the national reality in relation to that of other countries, particularly in the field of public policies and educational management. This is basic research in nature and bibliographical in terms of research method. The aim of this study was to discuss the importance of comparative education and the comparative method in educational research, in the area of educational policy, as well as to disseminate and propagate its relevance. It concludes that contextualizing comparative education shows its extreme relevance in research and teaching, in order to contribute to comparative literature.